

CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF DEPRESSION IN PATIENTS WITH PRIMARY HYPERPARATHYROIDISM

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Background. Problem of marginal psychoneurotic disturbances in patients with variousomatic pathologies has become urgent for the last decade. Psychoneurotic disturbances can be leading for quite a long time masking other manifestations of an underlying disease. prevalence of depressive conditions was found to grow for the last years; by 2020 depression is estimated to occupy a leading place in general structure of disease incidences.

Aim. The work was initiated to study depression manifestations in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism.

Materials and methods. Symptoms of anxiety and depression were assessed in 67 patients with primary hyperthyroidism aged from 16 to 30 years examined by means of Spielberger-Khanin,s test and Beck,s Depression Inventory.

Results. Parameters of both personal (n=62; 92,30%) and situational (n=60, 88,3%) anxiety were found high. (Spielberger-Khanin,s test). Fatigability (n=58, 89,4%), sleep disturbance (n=52, 79,7%), irritability (n=46, 68,6%), work inhibition (n=44,66.7V0), sadness (n=38,56,7), selfaccusations (n=33, 49,2%), pessimism and dissatisfaction (n=28, 41,70%), self dislike (n=26, 39,6%), were among clinical manifestations of depression registered among the examinees. (Beck's Depression Inventory).

Conclusions. Registered in most examinees with primary hyperthyroidism depressive reactions were found to aggravate severity of general illness. The study demonstrates necessity to timely diagnose affective impairments in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism to be corrected by means of combined therapy with antidepressants aiming at improvement of the patients' life quality.

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